

Deliverable 8.1: Project Website Established

Dissemination Level: Public (PU)

Owner

Name: Kite Innovation (Europe) Ltd
Lead Beneficiary: Kite Innovation (Europe) Ltd
Phone: +44 (0)1484 365 332
E-mail: hiperdias@kiteinnovation.com

Context

Author(s): James Clayton
Work Package: WP8
Task: All

Document Status

Version: 2.00
Last modified: 28/08/2017
Status: Released
Approved by: Marwan Abdou-Ahmed
Date Approved: 10/11/2017

Declaration: Any work or result described therein is genuinely a result of the Hiperdias project. Any other source will be properly referenced where and when relevant

Table of Contents

1	Scope.....	3
2	Introduction	4
3	Project Website.....	5
3.1	Aim	5
3.2	Objectives.....	5
4	Website Development	6
4.1	Website Platform	6
4.2	Website Design	7
4.3	Social Media	8
5	Future development of the Project Website and Strategy.....	9

1 Scope

The HIPERDIAS Project website has been developed to promote the effective dissemination of results and findings within the project. The website has been structured in a way that is informative, easy to navigate through and can target all different types of stakeholders.

This document should not be regarded to be a complete or final version. It is intended as a “living” document and as such will evolve throughout the duration of the project. This report will be reviewed by the Consortium on a yearly basis or when required, to continuously improve the HIPERDIAS dissemination activities. Updated versions of this report will be made available to the European Commission during Periodic Reporting.

HIPERDIAS dissemination activities will be monitored throughout the project in order to compare outputs against the Dissemination Strategy (which will be highlighted in Deliverable 8.4 & Deliverable 8.7), as well as identifying early potential issues and to comply with European Commission reporting requirements.

The website has been developed by Kite Innovation (Europe) Ltd (KITE), with the support of the Consortium Partners. KITE will be responsible for the overall co-ordination of the Project Website, as well as disseminating through Social Media outlets.

Any feedback on this document should be sent to the following people:

- Project Management Team – hiperdias@kiteinnovation.com
- Marwan Abdou Ahmed – Marwan.abdou-ahmed@ifsw.uni-stuttgart.de

2 Introduction

This document describes the aims and objectives with the Project Website and how they will be achieved throughout the lifetime of the project. Much of this information has been designed to continually review and develop the Dissemination Activities within the HIPERDIAS Project website and allow for continuous improvement.

The Consortium recognises the importance of communication within a project and has reviewed in detail the Horizon 2020 guidelines on [‘Communicating EU research and innovation guidance for project participants’](#).

3 Project Website

The purpose of having 'Aims and Objectives' is to provide direction and a sense of purpose for a project. A compelling aim is used to develop strategies and actionable tasks for the consortium to complete. Project 'Aims and Objectives' help a project direct all partners towards the same goals.

Without clear 'Aims and Objectives', a project is likely to have inefficient operations. It is difficult for partners to perform in a productive and coordinated manner on a daily/weekly basis without a clear sense of the purpose of their actions. With aims and goals, Work Package leaders can delegate different roles to partners in achieving shared objectives.

3.1 Aim

The aim of the HIPERDIAS Project website is *'to provide a central point of effective communication for the dissemination of results and to build on the Project Awareness to Stakeholders'*.

3.2 Objectives

The Consortium intentions are to try achieve this overall goal by establishing several objectives throughout the life of the Project. For the first six months of the Project, the objectives have been listed below:

1. Establish a Social Media platform and disseminate results monthly
2. Make available all Deliverable Reports that have a dissemination status as public within the Description of Action (DOA)
3. Disseminate Project Results on the Website (including: Publications, Conferences, Videos, Communication Kit and Press Releases)
4. Produce a monthly summary report on Google Analytics
5. Updating the Project Website on a regular basis
6. Develop hyperlinks from Partners website to Project Website
7. Establish new / modified objectives at the 2nd Consortium Meeting in September 2016

These objectives have been established for the first six months of the project and will evolve to include key performance indicators by the next Consortium Meeting in September 2016.

4 Website Development

4.1 Website Platform

Following the initial Website Research, KITE selected and identified three possible platforms to use for the project, as shown in the table below. The Table shows the Strengths and Weaknesses that were highlighted for the different Platforms:

Website Platform	Strengths	Weaknesses
Adobe Dreamweaver	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Easy to use Management System (for someone familiar with the system) - Training Tutorials and Templates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complexities in using the programme for non-users (e.g. with Coding). - Steep learning curve on how to use the system for new users. - Has additional costs, including: Purchasing Photographs (Shutterstock) and Widgets etc.
WordPress	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Easy to use Management System - Choice and flexibility of design (templates) - Free images 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - More costly on a yearly basis than WIX - No VIP Support
WIX	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Easy to use Management System - Choice and flexibility of design (templates) - Good Value for Money - Support Team and Community - Free images 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Visible advertisements on the free platform, however upgrade costs are still cheaper than WordPress. - Can't change templates easily - Not designed to manage complex e-commerce needs.

KITE opted to use WIX due to its functionality, free imagery and value for money. After a small cost analysis for the purposes of this project, it was calculated that WIX would be approximately €250 and €400 cheaper than using the WordPress and Dreamweaver.

The following domain name was also purchased at the start of the project and can be used as a direct link to the Website: <http://www.hiperdias.eu>

4.2 Website Design

The Website has been designed in an easy to navigate way that allows users to learn about the Project and its project results.

The Website is divided into several sections, including:

- **The Homepage:** This provides a basic overview of the project and includes News about the project
- **About the Project:** This contains the abstract, aims and objectives of the project.
- **Project Partners:** A list of the Partners and information about them, including links to the partner's websites and Partner logo.
- **Publications:** A list of all abstracts from the Consortium, Public Deliverables, Manuscripts, Marketing Material, Publication Strategy, Press Releases and Video.
- **Project News:** News about the Project. This will include progress made within the Project, including but not limited to:
 - **Deliverables** – Following the submission of any Deliverable Report to the European Commission. KITE will write a short summary (with partner approval) on the subject matter and make it available to the public. The aim of this exercise is to clearly demonstrate the work that has been completed within the HIPERDIAS Project, so that all stakeholders are kept regularly informed. It should be noted, that such summaries about Deliverable reports will not include confidential material, as this could lead to Intellectual Property issues.
 - **Highlights from each MGT Board Teleconference** – At each MGT Board Teleconference Meeting, each partner summarizes work completed from the previous month. It has been agreed within the Consortium, starting from September 2017, a highlight will be selected from this meeting and made available either via the Social Media or the Project Website.
 - **Conferences** – The Consortium have identified several Conferences which partners will be attending over the next several months and thus, each Conference will be published on the Project Website, summarizing both the significance of this event and why it is relevant to the HIPERDIAS Project.
 - **Any Other Business:** Whilst most the News and Social Media items have been covered in the list above, additional News Articles will be produced, for example significant results within the Project, attendance of meetings (Review and Consortium) to name a few.
- **Members Areas:** A secure area of the site where all documentation about the project will be kept. This is only available to members of the Consortium.
- **Useful Links:** Links to key information about H2020.

- **Contact us:** A contact form, where users can contact the Project Management Team.

The Project has also made acknowledgements to the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme and Photonics 21 in all pages of the website and links to Social Media platforms.

4.3 Social Media

KITE will use Twitter as their main social media platform for the project, and have already followed several of the main stakeholders within the HIPERDIAS Project, for example Research and Higher Communities (SPIE Photonics West, LaserShare), Funders (e.g. The European Commission and Photonics21), along with many others. As the News Articles and Twitter feeds increase throughout the duration of the Project, the Consortium expects that the number of followers will also increase.

5 Future development of the Project Website and Strategy

Partner consultation will take place at each Consortium Meeting to identify potential ways of improving the website and social media channels. It is acknowledged that successful implementation of the website aims and objectives also hinges on the combined efforts of all consortium members.

Partners are to inform the project management team when disseminating any activities in regards to the Project, which might include:

- Project Results
- Attendance of Conferences
- Images of Partners disseminating Project Results

The idea is to gather a large amount of information during the lifetime of the project and select the best items for dissemination.

**** END OF DOCUMENT ****